

Extent of Integration of Digitalised Business Education Curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

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Abstract

The study assessed the extent of Integration of Digitalised Business Education Curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria. The study was guided with 2 research questions and 6 hypotheses. The targeted population comprises 214; 113 lecturers in state universities and 101 lecturers in federal universities. A 35-item questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. The questionnaire was divided into two parts: Part A contained five (5) items of demographic variables of the respondents – Name of university, Type of university, Rank, Sex, Job experience. Part B contained 30 items based on the two (2) research questions; B1, To what extent is the application of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria? contained 17 items. B2, To what extent is the strategies for stimulating integration of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria? contained 13 items. The questionnaire was structured on a 4-point scale of responses: Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE), Very Low Extent (VLE). The questionnaire was validated by experts in business education, computer science and measurement and evaluation at the Delta State University, Abraka. The instrument has the following reliability results: Research question 1. $r = 0.86$ and Research question 2. $r = 0.81$. A total of 214 copies of the questionnaire were administered to 214 lecturers. A total of 191 were fully completed and returned. There was return rate is 89.25%. The data collected were weighted and analyzed as follows: Very High Extent (VHE) – 4 points, High Extent (HE)- 3 points, Low Extent (LE)- 2 points, Very Low Extent (VLE)-1 point. In decision rule, any item with a mean score of 2.5 and above is regarded as High Extent while any item below 2.5 is regarded as Low Extent. The findings of research question one are Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI), The use of PowerPoint projection for instructional delivery, Use of Skype to share instruction with students and AUTOCAD for teaching and learning in schools among others. The findings of research question two are Organisation of digitalised instruction conference for lecturers, Organisation workshop for lecturers among others. The following recommendations were made: University authorities should provide more facilities to teach students on how to acquire skills on use of skype to share instruction with students and AUTOCAD for teaching and learning in schools among others.

Keywords: Integration, Business Education, Digital Technology, Instructional Delivery, Universities.

Introduction

Business education is a part of vocational education and skill-based course of study that is widely promoted for its relevance in the contemporary competitive global labour market. Business education as described by Suleiman (2017) is an area of education which deals with the study of the subject related to or dealing with the art of shorthand writing, typewriting, accounting, business

mathematics, secretarial duties, and commerce and office practice (Utoware & Igberaharha, 2024). According to Osuala (2004) Business Education is a broad district of knowledge that deals with a nation's fiscal structure and also identifies and explains the rate of business gratification and experience that train persons for valuable involvement as citizens, workers and consumers. The objectives of Business Education as stated by Edokpolor and Egbri (2017) include: to prepare students for specific career in office occupations, equip students with the requisite skills for job creation and entrepreneurship and expose students to knowledge about business, including a good blend with computer technology, which incorporates Information and Communication Technology. In order to achieve the goal of business education, as stated in the business education curriculum, there is the need for integration of digital instruction by the lecturers to facilitate teaching and learning.

The concept of business education curriculum is very relevant for the purpose of integration of digital instruction. Business education curriculum involves the courses that are introduced into the programs for the purpose of skill acquisition. Such courses involve accounting, office technology, marketing and entrepreneurship. Amesi & Sobere (2024) note that business education curriculum implementation to a large extent connotes the attainment of objectives and goals of this educational programme through the routines efforts of all stakeholders (teacher, students and administrators). When this courses are introduced into the business education curriculum, it will result in acquisition of relevant skills for employment in order to enable the graduands to be self-employed. Business education curriculum could be more effective if there is introduction of digital skills for content delivery.

Digital instruction emphasizes all forms of teaching and learning experiences that involve the use of audio, video, and visual contents to impart knowledge. (Utoware & Igberaharha, 2024) This type of instruction engages multiple learner senses, including sight, sound, and in some instances touch, where the media is interactive (Centre for Teaching, learning and mentoring, 2021). Digital instructions are becoming increasingly prominent methods of teaching for teachers in the contemporary education system. Shukla (2022) submitted that digital instructions require organized electronic resources to support instructions. Tosh, Doan, Woo and Henry (2019) note that digital instructions are online and technology-based teaching and learning platforms. The goal of the digital instructional technique is to provide a clear picture of instruction to help encourage increased comprehension of digital learning (State Educational Technology Directors Association, 2019). Effective planning is essential when considering digital learning for quality instructional experience and skill acquisition of learners. Knowledge and skill acquisition in Business education is very crucial in the present world of work; this can better be achieved through integration of digitalized instruction in the business education curriculum in Nigerian Universities.

Statement of the Problem

Business education and the utilization of digital resources in teaching have been acknowledged as potent and viable tools for skill development, self-empowerment, job creation and economic survival. It is prepared to turn out producer-graduates into the society who would contribute more significantly to the economic activities of the Nigerian economy. It is surprising that many Business education graduates still join the queue of unemployed graduates because they left the university as consumer-graduates who lack productive skills for self-employment. The world is technologically getting advanced. Digital resources are vital tools needed for facilitating teaching and learning in business education programme in Nigerian Universities.

Business education is education for and about business. This is the relevant stage required in business education programme to enable the graduands to be self-employed and self-reliant. There are complaints that business education graduates lack the relevant technology skills as a result of poor digital instruction in business education in Nigerian Universities. The problem of the study therefore is, to what extent is Integration of Digitalised Business Education Curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to assess the extent of Integration of Digitalised Business Education Curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives are:

1. To assess the extent of application of digitalized instructional technologies in business education curriculum.
2. To assess strategies for integration of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. To what extent is the application of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria?
2. To what extent are the strategies for stimulating integration of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between male and female lecturers on application of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria?
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between male and female lecturers on strategies for stimulating integration of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria?
3. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between State and Federal Lecturers on application of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria?
4. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between State and Federal Lecturers on strategies for stimulating integration of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria?
5. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between experienced and less-experienced Lecturers on application of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria?
6. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between experienced and less-experienced Lecturers on strategies for stimulating integration of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria?

Scope of the Study

This study assessed the extent of integration of digitalised business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria. The study was restricted to South-South Public Universities in Nigeria. All lecturers were involved in the study with their level of experience and their locations.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey design. The descriptive survey is suitable because there is no manipulation of data (Okoro, 2024). The study was guided with 2 research questions and 6 hypotheses. The targeted population comprises 214. The breakdown is 113 business education lecturers in state universities and 101 business education lecturers in federal universities. The entire population was used for the study, since the population was manageable. Therefore, there was no sampling.

A 35-item questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. The questionnaire was divided into two parts: Part A contained five (5) items of demographic variables of the respondents – Name of university, Type of university, Rank, Sex, Job experience. Part B contained 30 items based on the two (2) research questions in a cluster form: B1, To what extent is the application of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria? contained 17 items. B2, To what extent are the strategies for integration of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria? contained 13 items. The questionnaire was structured on a 4-point scale of responses: Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE), Very Low Extent (VLE). There was face and content validity of the instrument. The questionnaire was given to two experts in computer science, three experts in measurement and evaluation and two experts in business education at the Delta State University, Abraka. The experts made necessary corrections and suggestions which were effected before the final copy was written. In order to ensure the internal consistency of the instrument, a total of 15 copies of the questionnaire were administered to 15 lecturers in business education at Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti in South West Nigeria which is not part of the study. The data obtained were subjected to Cronbach Alpha which yielded the following reliability co-efficient. Research question 1. $r = 0.86$ and Research question 2. $r = 0.81$. A total of 214 copies of the questionnaire were administered to 214 lecturers. 113 lecturers state universities and 101 lecturers in federal universities. 191 were fully completed and returned within a period of three weeks. There was return rate of 89.25%. The data collected were weighted and analyzed as follows: Very High Extent (VHE) – 4 points, High Extent (HE)- 3 points, Low Extent (LE)- 2 points, Very Low Extent (VLE)-1 point. In decision rule, any item with a mean score of 2.5 and above is regarded as High Extent while any item below 2.5 is regarded as Low Extent. T-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. If t-calculated value is less than t-critical, hypothesis is accepted. On the other hand, if the t-calculated value is greater than t-critical, hypotheses is rejected.

Results

The chapter presents the results and discusses findings that align with the research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question 1: To what extent is the application of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria?

Table 1: Extent of the application of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria. N = 191

S/N	Items on application of digitalized instructional technologies in business education	\bar{x}	Std. Dev.	Decision
1.	Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI)	2.55	0.88	High Extent
2.	Use of Skype to share instruction with students	2.43	0.73	Low Extent
3.	Use of computer programmes	2.58	0.71	High Extent
4.	Use of software	2.52	0.85	High Extent
5.	Video conference	2.57	0.74	High Extent
6.	Use of simulation games	2.65	0.72	High Extent
7.	The use of Zoom for meetings	2.61	0.75	High Extent
8.	E-book Reader	2.66	0.77	High Extent
9.	Streaming videos for students' learning	2.59	0.82	High Extent
10.	AUTOCAD for teaching and learning in schools	2.32	0.70	Low Extent
11.	Use of advanced calculators	2.64	0.84	High Extent
12.	YouTube instruction for students learning	2.48	0.71	Low Extent
13.	Use of Computer Based Test (CBT) for students' assessment.	2.89	0.89	High Extent
14.	Web Based Test (WBT) for students' assessment and evaluation	2.41	0.74	Low Extent
15.	Use of smart phones,	2.68	0.85	High Extent
16.	Use of laptops	2.77	0.82	High Extent
17.	The use of PowerPoint projection for instructional delivery	3.02	0.81	High Extent
Aggregate Mean		2.61	0.78	High Extent
Criterion Mean		2.50		

The data presented in table 1 shows that the mean rating of the responses of the respondents on items 1-17 are between 2.32 and 3.02. only items 2, 10, 12 and 14 have mean scores below 2.5 and to a low extent. All other items have means score above 2.5 and are to a high extent.

Research Question 2: To what extent are the strategies for integration of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria?

Table 2: Extent of the strategies for stimulating integration of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria. N = 191

S/N	Items on strategies for stimulating the integration digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum	\bar{x}	Std. Dev.	Decision
1.	Organisation of digitalised instruction conference for lecturers	2.63	0.84	High Extent
2.	Organisation of workshop for lecturers	2.55	0.73	High Extent
3.	Adequate funding of digital instructional technologies	2.92	0.87	High Extent
4.	Recruiting computer literate business educators	2.74	0.76	High Extent
5.	Recruiting ICT literate business educators	2.88	0.91	High Extent
6.	Adequate provision of digital instructional facilities	2.71	0.90	High Extent
7.	Adoption of digital-based curriculum in-line with global trend	2.74	0.88	High Extent

8.	Improved skill training of business educators	2.86	0.89	High Extent
9.	Effective monitoring	2.84	0.86	High Extent
10.	Creation of suitable environment in school	2.79	0.81	High Extent
11.	Well equipped laboratories	2.78	0.73	High Extent
12.	Private public partnership arrangement	2.55	0.81	High Extent
13.	Provision of foreign grant for supply of digital instructional facilities	2.89	0.81	High Extent
Aggregate Mean		2.74	0.83	High Extent
Criterion Mean				

The data presented in table 2 shows that the mean rating of the responses of the respondents on items 1 - 13 are between 2.55 and 2.92. All are above 2.5 and to a high extent.

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between male and female lecturers on application of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation ratings of male and female lecturers on application of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	df	t. value	Decision
Male	119	2.78	0.86	1.06	189	1.96	Accepted
Female	72	2.54	0.91				

Since the t-cal (1.06) is less than t. value 1.96 at significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Ho2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between male and female lecturers on strategies for stimulating integration of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Table 4: Mean and standard deviation ratings of male and female lecturers on strategies for stimulating integration of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	df	t. value	Decision
Male	119	2.83	0.79	0.97	189	1.96	Accepted
Female	72	2.75	0.86				

Since the t-cal (0.97) is less than t. value 1.96 at significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Ho3: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between State and Federal lecturers on application of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Table 5: Mean ratings between State and Federal lecturers on application of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	df	t. value	Decision
State	102	2.61	0.83	1.02	189	1.96	Accepted
Federal	89	2.56	0.74				

Since the t-cal (1.02) is less than t. value 1.96 at significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Ho4: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between State and Federal lecturers on strategies for stimulating integration of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Table 6: Mean ratings between state and federal lecturers on strategies for stimulating integration of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	df	t. value	Decision
State	102	2.71	0.94	0.92	189	1.96	Accepted
Federal	89	2.64	0.93				

Since the t-cal (0.92) is less than t. value 1.96 at significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Ho5: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between experienced and less-experienced lecturers on application of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Table 6: Mean ratings between experienced and less-experienced lecturers on application of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	df	t. value	Decision
Experienced	138	2.83	0.80	0.99	189	1.96	Accepted
Less-experienced	53	2.75	0.82				

Since the t-cal (0.99) is less than t. value 1.96 at significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Ho6: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between experienced and less-experienced lecturers on strategies for stimulating integration of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Table 6: Mean ratings between experienced and less-experienced lecturers on strategies for stimulating integration of digitalised instructional technologies in business education curriculum in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	df	t. value	Decision
Experienced	138	2.62	0.79	1.04	189	1.96	Accepted
Less-experienced	53	2.54	0.93				

Since the t-cal (1.04) is less than t. value 1.96 at significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Discussion of findings

The findings of research question 1 are: computer assisted instruction (CAI), use of skype to share instruction with students, use of computer programmes, use of software, video conference, use of simulation games, the use of zoom for meetings, e-book reader, streaming videos for students’ learning, AutoCAD for teaching and learning in schools, use of advanced calculators, Youtube instruction for students learning, use of computer based test (CBT) for students’ assessment, web based test (WBT) for students’ assessment and evaluation, use of smart phones, use of laptops and the use of PowerPoint projection for instructional delivery. The result of hypotheses of research question one. The results of hypotheses of research question one shows that no significant difference is seen in the mean ratings of the variables such as male and female, state and federal universities lecturers and experienced and less experienced lecturers. The hypotheses are therefore accepted. The study is consistent with the earlier studies of Utoware and Igbehara (2024) which identified digitalised instructional technologies in business education.

The findings of research question 2 are: organisation of digitalised instruction conference for lecturers, organisation workshop for lecturers, adequate funding of digital instructional technologies, recruiting computer literate business educators, recruiting ICT literate business educators, adequate provision of digital instructional facilities, adoption of digital-based curriculum in-line with global trend, improved skill training of business educators, effective monitoring, creation of suitable environment in school, well equipped laboratories, private public partnership arrangement, provision of foreign grant for supply of digital instructional facilities. The results of hypotheses of research question 2 also show no significant difference between the variables an the hypotheses are also accepted. The findings of research question 2 are consistent with the earlier studies of Utoware and Igbehara (2024) which studied strategic integration of digitalised instructional technologies in business education.

Conclusion

Business education is a part of the education that enables graduates to have more skills in office technology, accounting, marketing, Information and Communication Technology. The success of the graduands in the world of work depends on the level of digital skills acquired in their course of study. It is therefore paramount that business education curriculum is focused on instructional strategies that will enable the graduands to have multi task skills in the present technological era.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made for the study:

1. University authorities should provide more facilities to teach students to acquire skills on use of skype to share instruction with other students
2. University authorities should encourage use of AUTOCAD for teaching and learning in universities.
3. There should be adequate funding of digital instructional technologies in universities.
4. University authorities should work towards securing foreign grants for supply of digital instructional facilities.

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